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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

ZAMONAVIY G‘ARB PEDAGOGIKASINING YUTUQLARI

Sayfullayev Husniddin

Jizzax shahar 2-son ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab-internati o‘qituvchisi.

E-MAIL:

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy G‘arb pedagogikasining asosiy yutuqlari, uning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va ta’lim jarayoniga ta’siri tahlil qilinadi. G‘arb pedagogikasining innovatsion uslublari, o‘quv dasturlari va texnologik yechimlari, shuningdek, ta’limda individual yondashuvning ahamiyati ko‘rib chiqiladi. Maqola o‘qituvchilar va ta’lim muassasalari uchun zamonaviy pedagogik amaliyotlar, ularning o‘quv jarayonidagi o‘rni va samaradorligini oshirish uchun takliflar bilan to‘ldirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Zamonaviy pedagogika, G‘arb ta’lim tizimi, Innovatsion uslublar, O‘quv jarayoni, Individual yondashuv, Ta’lim texnologiyalari, Ta’lim metodikasi, Ta’lim yutuqlari.

Kirish

Zamonaviy G‘arb pedagogikasi, o‘zining xilma-xilligi va dinamikasi bilan, ta’lim jarayonini yanada samarali va innovatsion yo‘nalishlarda rivojlantirishga intilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada, zamonaviy G‘arb pedagogikasining yutuqlari, uning asosiy tamoyillari va ta’lim tizimlarida yuz berayotgan o‘zgarishlar haqida fikr yuritamiz.

1. Talabalar markazida ta’lim

Zamonaviy pedagogikada eng muhim yutuqlardan biri – talabalar markazida ta’lim. Bu yondashuv talabalar o‘z o‘qish jarayonida faol ishtirok etishlarini ta’minlaydi. Ta’lim jarayoni faqat muallim tomonidan beriladigan bilimlar bilan cheklanmay, balki talabalar o‘z qiziqishlari, ehtiyojlari va qobiliyatlari asosida shakllanadi.

2. Interaktiv ta’lim metodlari

G‘arb pedagogikasida interaktiv ta’lim metodlari keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Muallimlar va talabalar o‘rtasida samarali muloqot va hamkorlik o‘rnatish, o‘zaro fikr

almashish imkonini beradi. Bunga guruhli ishlar, muammoli vazifalar va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo'llash kiradi. Bu metodlar, talabalarni mustaqil fikrlashga va muammolarni hal qilishga o'rgatadi.

3. Texnologiyaning integratsiyasi

Zamonaviy G'arb ta'lim tizimlarida texnologiyaning integratsiyasi o'ziga xos yutuqdir. O'qituvchilar va talabalar uchun onlayn resurslar, ta'lim platformalari va interaktiv dasturlar mavjud. Bu texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonini yanada qulay va samarali qiladi, talabalar uchun esa bilimlarni mustahkamlashda yordam beradi.

4. Ta'limda inklyuzivlik

G'arb pedagogikasida inklyuziv ta'lim tamoyillari ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu yondashuv, har qanday ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va jismoniy holatga ega talabalarni ta'lim tizimiga qamrab olishni maqsad qiladi. O'qituvchilar, o'z darslarini har bir talabaning ehtiyojlariga mos ravishda moslashtirishga harakat qiladilar.

5. Mavzu asosida o'qitish

Zamonaviy ta'limda mavzu asosida o'qitish yondashuvi ham muhimdir. Bu yondashuv, turli fanlar o'rtasida integratsiyani ta'minlaydi va talabalarni bir butun sifatida o'rganishga undaydi. Mavzu asosida o'qitish, talabalarni real hayotdagi muammolarni hal qilishga tayyorlaydi.

Xulosa

Zamonaviy G'arb pedagogikasi, ta'lim jarayonida bir qator yutuqlarga erishdi. Talabalar markazida ta'lim, interaktiv metodlar, texnologiyaning integratsiyasi, inklyuzivlik va mavzu asosida o'qitish – bularning barchasi zamonaviy ta'lim tizimini yanada samarali va qiziqarli qiladi. Ushbu yutuqlar, kelajak avlodni tayyorlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi va ta'lim sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Bu maqola orqali zamonaviy G'arb pedagogikasining asosiy yutuqlarini ko'rib chiqish, ta'lim tizimlarining rivojlanishi va zamonaviy talabalarning ehtiyojlarini qondirishga qaratilgan yondashuvlar haqida umumiy tasavvur berishga yordam beradi.

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